

Scarlett Johansson does not profit from a cheerleader effect, but John C. Reilly does

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Authors' Note

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose. Materials and data are available at

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The “cheerleader effect” describes the phenomenon whereby faces are perceived as being more attractive when flanked by other faces than when they are perceived in isolation (Messner et al., 2021; Walker & Vul, 2014). Some boundary conditions of the cheerleader effect have been tested in recent studies. The cheerleader effect occurs in natural group settings as well as when viewing single pictures of faces (Walker & Vul, 2014); it also occurs when viewing computer-generated faces (Ying et al., 2019). Neither the size of the group (Walker & Vul, 2014) nor the position of the target face (Carragher et al., 2018) moderates the cheerleader effect; however, the attractiveness of the flanking faces plays a moderating role: the less attractive the flanking faces, the greater the cheerleader effect (Ying et al., 2019).

The aim of this paper is to document a study which gives evidence that the cheerleader effect does not occur with extremely attractive faces, neither if they are flanked by other highly attractive faces nor when they are flanked by less attractive faces. This ceiling effect is in line with several theoretical explanations. One example is the general evaluability theory, which states that observers use external criteria for their evaluation only if the internal criteria are insufficient (Hsee, 1996; Hsee & Zhang, 2010). Observers’ internal criteria are sufficient to estimate the attractiveness of extremely attractive people like Scarlett Johansson. The control condition with ordinary faces replicates the cheerleader effect and provides further evidence that the change in evaluation mode from a situation where observers of no external standards of comparison (face without a group) to a situation where observers could use external standards for their comparison (face within a group) is a sufficient condition for the cheerleader effect to occur (for a review see Messner et al., 2021).

Method

Participants

A total of 605 participants completed the study, with 19 failing to pass an attention check and being dismissed. Of the remaining 586 participants, 240 were female, 343 were male, and three identified as other. The mean age was 37.16 ($SD = 11.23$, $range = 18$ to 73).

Design

The study used a 3 (Flankers' attractiveness) \times 2 (Targets' attractiveness) between-subjects design. One-third of the participants only viewed the targets, one-third viewed the targets flanked by two extremely high attractive faces, and one-third viewed the targets flanked by ordinary attractive faces. In addition, the targets' attractiveness was manipulated: one-half of the participants were shown only targets of extremely high attractiveness, while the other half was shown only targets of ordinary attractiveness. Note that the extremely high attractive target faces did not differ in their attractiveness from the extremely high attractive flanker faces. Likewise, target faces of ordinary attractiveness did not differ in their attractiveness from flanking faces of ordinary attractiveness.

The order in which the faces appeared was counterbalanced, as was the side on which the flankers were presented. The assignment of the conditions was random.

Procedure and Materials

Dependent variable. After participants provided their informed consent, they were instructed to rate the attractiveness of the face in the middle of the screen on a scale from 0 (not at all attractive) to 100 (extremely attractive). Each participant rated two faces. For each face, the mean attractiveness rating served as the dependent variable.

Data availability. The data are available at

https://osf.io/ud5k4/?view_only=6a9fad2c670949e38080597482c406a5

Attention check. Typically, online experiments contain an attention check to filter out participants who did not read the instructions carefully. After measuring the dependent variable, participants were shown a picture of a dog's face and were instructed to click on a scale from 0 to 100 within the range of 20 to 30. This served as an attention check.

Manipulation check. After the attention check, participants rated the attractiveness of the flankers. To compare flankers with target face attractiveness, only data from participants who had previously evaluated targets without flankers were analyzed so that they evaluated the flankers' face attractiveness when they viewed them the first time.

Ethical approval statement. The study was carried out in accordance with the recommendation of the Federal Act on Research involving Human Beings of the Swiss Confederation. The studies were approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Business, Economics, and Social Science of the University of Bern (Project Number:102019).

Results

Manipulation Check

The manipulation of the target's attractiveness was successful. All analyses of the manipulation check are based on evaluations of faces which were presented in isolation. The targets of extremely high attractiveness ($M = 82.98$, $SD = 16.31$) were rated as more attractive than targets of ordinary attractiveness ($M = 35.12$, $SD = 16.83$), $t(188) = 19.91$, $p < .001$.

Furthermore, targets of ordinary attractiveness ($M = 35.12$, $SD = 16.83$) were rated as equally attractive as flankers of ordinary attractiveness ($M = 36.34$, $SD = 24.62$), $t(235.79) =$

0.46, $p = .65$. However, the attractiveness of the flanking faces of extremely high attractiveness did not correspond to the target face attractiveness: targets of extremely high attractiveness ($M = 82.98$, $SD = 16.31$) were rated as more attractive than flankers of extremely high attractiveness ($M = 76.07$, $SD = 19.62$), $t(225.04) = 2.97$, $p < .01$.

Main Results

All reported results are based on two-sided tests. A between-subject analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that highly attractive faces were rated as more attractive ($M = 82.98$, $SD = 15.75$) than faces of low attractiveness ($M = 36.64$, $SD = 18.79$) $F(1, 582) = 1061.00$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.646$.

Furthermore, the target faces' attractiveness was marginally influenced by the flankers, $F(2, 582) = 2.29$, $p = .102$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.008$. A post hoc Tukey test showed that the target faces were perceived as marginally more attractive when flanked by faces of low attractiveness ($M = 61.92$, $SD = 27.47$) than when they were flanked by faces of high attractiveness ($M = 58.44$, $SD = 30.19$), $p = .11$. However, no difference in the perceived attractiveness ratings were found between faces with flankers of low attractiveness ($M = 61.92$, $SD = 27.47$) and faces without flankers ($M = 59.05$, $SD = 29.14$), $p = .23$, or faces with flankers of high attractiveness ($M = 58.45$, $SD = 30.19$) and faces without flankers, $p = .94$.

A marginally significant interaction between the attractiveness of the targets and that of the flankers was observed $F(2, 582) = 2.85$, $p = .06$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.01$. This indicates that unattractive faces may benefit more from being flanked by faces of low attractiveness than highly attractive faces. These results do not support the hierarchical encoding hypothesis or the contrast hypothesis and are more aligned with the evaluability hypothesis.

Figure 1: Changes in the attractiveness of faces of ordinary and extremely high attractiveness due to flankers of ordinary and extremely high attractiveness.

Note. This figure illustrates the changes in the mean and the confidence interval (95%) in the attractiveness of target faces of ordinary and extremely high attractiveness when they are not flanked, and when they are flanked by faces of ordinary or extremely high attractiveness.

Conclusion

The study provides evidence that extremely highly attractive faces do not profit from flanking faces, and for ordinary attractive faces the study replicates recent work that the cheerleader effect does not need a contrast with flanking face attractiveness. Even equally attractive flankers cause a cheerleader effect for ordinary attractive faces, because of a change in the evaluation mode (for a review see Messner et al., 2021)

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